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Review Article

**INVISIBLE CELL AND UNFATHOMABLE UNIVERSE
DEMONSTRATES THE SOVEREIGNTY OF GOD**Ahmed Raza^{1*}, Sahibzada Baz Muhammed², Ghulam Muhammed Jaffer³

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Abstract:

Every person in the world has some questions about the existence of universe and himself in his mind. In response to these, two thoughts are presented according to religious point of view. First, everything is created by Almighty God and second, materialists explain that whole system of universe is a coincident and it has a beginning out of Big Bang. The life was originated by a single cell and the first cell was originated spontaneously without any creator.

In order to know about this fact, it was essential to examine the structure of cell because initially it was thought the cell is only a balloon full of liquid. But by the help of latest science and technology, we know the cell is a miracle, having a very complicated system.

The study of cell and DNA proves that it is impossible for it to come into existence by itself or by chance. This whole unique system is a witness that there is a great creator who has created it by His great wisdom.

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INTRODUCTION:

The subject of this article is about Cell, the building block of the human body and of every species of plants and animals. It looks like that this topic belongs to the realm of biology and chemistry. But in fact, the biological information about the cell is presented in the text books, in a slightly wrong logical context. As soon as a child starts observing the world around him, many questions arise in his mind. But in response, the answer that the child receives is, everything around us was appeared by chance as a result of a big explosion that took place, and everything on earth came into existence by coincidence. But if the same child is raised in a knowledgeable society, the answer would be different: that everything is manifestation of God's endless knowledge, and everything around us is a blessing of God. If He had not willed nothing could have happened. But the child seldom gets the before mentioned response at the name of "scientific" logic and his curiosity is put to sleep by this type of answers to his queries. When he asks about an apple's taste or a flower's smell, in all probability he would receive the same predictable answers: trees and plants have been producing fruits and flowers for millions of years as a natural phenomenon. At school, he learns a scientific explanation behind all creatures and all events. Later, biology, physics and chemistry lessons teaches him about the working of human body or nature. He learns biological details of plants, facts about photosynthesis and their structure. But he never learns about the source of intelligence, discipline and balance behind it. [1]

In order to fully appreciate the marvels in any construction or invention, the very first thing one needs to do is to assemble detailed information about it. For example someone who lacks full, detailed knowledge concerning the Pyramids of Egypt, may consider it simply, innumerable piles of stones. But when detail and secrets are explained, it can astonish anyone. An even greater complexity is also displayed in the human body, which possesses numerous marvelous features in addition to the perfection of its external appearance. Without learning and reflecting on these details, we cannot come to a full realization of the miracles occurring in our body. [2]

Almighty God, the Creator of all universe(s), all living things and human beings without doubt created the incredible system of cell, with their flawless systems and breathtaking abilities. Learning about them can assist us in understanding the infinite knowledge, intelligence, greatness and glory of our Lord, the creator of all these marvels.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

According to the Theory of Evolution, the life was originated by a single cell. But how was the first cell originated? The evolutionists say, two hundred billion years ago, some chemical reactions of oxygen, carbon and hydrogen formed first ever cell by chance. This idea was presented at the time when science and technology was at the beginning stages of development. That's why it was not possible to see bacteria with naked eye. Aristotle presented the same idea that the life was originated spontaneously from the non-living things, and this non-living material was found in moisture of the atmosphere where life began. [3]

Darwin's theory was based on the same idea that he stated as: "Species have been produced by ordinary generation." [4]

Followers of Darwin also believed and acknowledged the same that the cell is only a small balloon full of liquid.

The beginning of life was a coincidence, and was simple. In order to know about this fact, it is essential to examine the structure of cell. All the living creatures, whether it is grass, or leaf of a tree, an insect, or animal, even the human beings are composed of different types of cells. This means cell is the basic unit of every living creature. When these basic units joined together, it becomes a body. The cell division is a continuous process that not only increases number of cells but it heals and changes the entire human system whenever and wherever necessary. The entire human body which includes eyes, ears, lungs, heart and brain and every other internal and external organ comes into existence by the division of cell. A new born baby's body consists of almost two trillion (2,00,00,00,00,000) cells. If we put a cell under a microscopic observation, we see a completely different world in it. The size of a cell ranges from about 10 to 100 micron (micron=0.001mm). This unseen body which can't be seen by naked eye has a much disciplined system. A cell has a communication and transportation system as complicated as that of a big city. It produces its own energy, hormones and raw material. It has its own production system and also can store its productions. Cell has a very strong defense system. This information is just unbelievable and initial about the cell. [5]

Due to modern scientific research cell is just like an open book in front of us, and day by day our knowledge about it is increasing. The spontaneous or coincidental creation of cell is impossible. It cannot come into existence by its own. Many people tried

for years to create a cell but they badly failed. Haroon Yahya writes: "If we take atoms of different elements and combine them in different numbers and shapes which would result in a number of molecules, even then the wisdom and awareness would not be produced. Whether these molecules are small or big, simple or complicated, it would not make any difference, none of these can at all create a mind which would be able to think and act." [6]

A complete cell is beyond our range of creation. We cannot even create a part of cell such as mitochondria or ribosomes. Since we are not able to create a cell, how does it come into existence by its own self, or by chance? It will never happen that a factory is created all by itself, starts working and begins to prepare things on its own, or that different parts of a watch will combine all by itself and make a whole new watch. Hence there are no evidences which support the claim of the evolutionists that one specie changed to another. Thus Michal Denton said in his book, *Evolution: A theory in crisis*, "German zoologist Bernhard Ranch was able to provide a long list of prominent authorities, who have been inclined to the view that macro evolution (changes across species) cannot explained in term of micro evolutionary processes (changes within species) or any other currently known mechanism." [7]

According the theory of evolution all the living creatures' originated from a single living cell. In middle ages, when people knew less about natural laws, they believed on a biogenesis. It was so because of few wrong observations. It was thought that the insects were born by themselves from wasted food and it was also considered that after a few days of putting wheat on dirty cloths, mouse was born. By same method insects were born in meat. This theory was known as theory of spontaneous generation. But the experiments of two scientists Francis Co Redi and Louis Pasture completely rejected these theories and proved them wrong upon which the evolution theory was based. So the claim that life originated from non-living things was buried in the graveyard of history. [8]

In twentieth century a Russian biologist Alexander Operon wrote many articles in 1930 and tried to prove that a cell can be created by chance. But to prove this, he experimented for many years but failed. In his book *origin of life*, he accepted his failure in these words: "This is also evident because present day particles of proteins are not only extremely complicated in structure but are also well adapted to carrying out particular biologically important functions. Enzymes, hormones, etc. seem

to be perfectly rationally constructed organs of living protoplasm". Therefore the hypothesis that they arose primarily in some way, and that protoplasm itself was later gradually built up from them, reminds one of the ancient Greek philosopher story who believed that at first there arose separate, independent organs: Out of it (Earth) necks, arms, eyes, and feet emerged. Later on, these disunited members joined themselves together and in this way there arose various animals and people. [9]

Cell consist of different things, One of them is protein. It is not possible to make a small portion of protein, which is called a molecule. Frank Elian, who is the professor of biological physics in Canada, writes: "Proteins, which is a very important part of cells in all living creatures, consists of five elements, carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, oxygen and Sulphur. Molecule consist of 40,000 atoms of these elements in universe 92 chemical elements are spread unorderly. What are the chances, from these heap of 92 unordered elements these five elements separated and got together so perfectly that a molecule came into existence by itself? The quantity of matter which continually shacked, and the period in which this work could be completed, can be calculated. [10]

Through the theory of probability, it can be calculated easily that by coincidence, proteins structure cannot come into existence. Amino acids have 20 different types. For instance a small volume molecule consists of 288 amino acids. In this molecule 24 amino acids can be layout by 10 300 different ways. In all these sequences only by one method, the required molecule can be produced. All other settings or layouts are useless or dangerous for biological life. In other words a chance for proteins molecule to come into existence by itself is one from 10^{300} . Practically it means the chances are zero. [11]

In every cell, proteins, amino acids, nucleus, DNA (Deoxyribose nucleic acid) molecules are found, in its life expectancy presence is a testimony of truth that a there is an entity, who has given them life.

A scientist Charles o-u Jean Gaea from Switzerland calculated this and his research proved that the chance of this incidental event is 10^{160} . It should be kept in mind that it means that 10 would be multiplied 160 times. Therefore it is only a hypothesis. It is not possible to explain it in the language of mathematics. Only for a molecule, to come into existence, billion times present matter of whole universe would be required which will be shaped after gathering and the result of this process

would come after billions of years approximately after (243^{10}) years. [12]

Discovery of DNA:

Times after 1950 holds a historical significance in the world of Biology because during this half century scientists revealed many key secrets of life. A great job among them was to discover DNA and to understand the message of the Creator the Almighty God.

The startup of every living organism is from a tiny sphere no larger than a dot on this page, called cell which is not visible through naked eye. Within that microscopic ball there is over six feet of DNA (Deoxyribonucleic acid), all coiled up. Inside that DNA is the entire code for what you will become, all your organs and all your features. The DNA itself is strung out within long coiling strips. DNA is the carrier of the inheritance code in living organisms that acts like a microscopic computer with a built-in memory. DNA stores a fantastic number of "blueprints" and the right time and place issues orders for distant parts of the body to build its cells and structures. We have heard of genes and a chromosome, inside each cell of the body is nucleus. Inside that nucleus are, among other complicated things, chromosomes. Inside the chromosomes are genes. The genes are attached to chromosomes like beads on a chain. Inside the genes is a complicated chemical structure we called DNA units with in it. Each gene has a thousand or more such DNA units within it. Inside each cell are tens of thousands of such genes, grouped in 23 pairs of chromosomes. [13]

In the second half of the 19th century 'Gregor Mendel' was the first scientist who experimented on pea plant. He ended up with the result that one generation of the flowers transfers its colors and features to the other. He also came to know that the inherited features consist of small units, which are named as their factors. In the 20th century after further research in this field, Mendel's sought term 'factors' was named as 'Genes'. In 1953, further researches on DNA molecule stirred the World of Science. DNA is a stunning article. The combined length of the twisted DNA strands (double helix) if taken out and lined up would be about 10 times more than that of the distance from the earth to the moon.

When scientists observed the white cells of blood serum secreted by a wound, an extremely complicated structure was seen in the center (nucleus) of the cell which was named as nucleic acid. In 1929, the further studies showed that this

acid is of two types, DNA and RNA. Excluding the red blood cells DNA is found in every cell of the body. A cell is so small that 1 million cells can easily adjust on the tip of a pin whereas our body is made up 100 trillion such cells. DNA is present in the cell and performs all its tasks as if it's the supervisor who is responsible for the construction and the breakdown of a building. The cell is a masterpiece of nature whereas the DNA present in it is a miracle. DNA is the abbreviation of Deoxyribonucleic acid. The DNA of the cell which comes into existence by the chromosomes of both the parents, is like two twisted strings. The preparation of organs, their texture, development, performance, the color of hair and eyes, the individuals nature, the sickness he would be suffering from in the future, the impact of inherited diseases, the features inherited from the ancestors, thus all the details from the beginning of human life till death are present on the DNA of cell in the form of codes.

All this process could be understood by considering the construction of a building. Firstly, the architect designs the map for the building to be constructed then this designed map is given to the contractor who constructs the building. The details about the construction are present on the DNA and according to these details the building is constructed. The role of contractor in cell is played by RNA (ribonucleic acid). RNA understands the details well and starts the construction under the supervision of DNA. For this purpose RNA catalyzes the assembly of amino acids into protein chains, which form muscles, yet that organ will form whose instructions would be issued by DNA. The amazing fact is that DNA is present in every cell of the body and has all the technical information and abilities that it can make any organ of the body. This means that the cells of ears have the ability to make feet instead of ears. But cells won't do this. Why won't they do so? Who issues the coded information on DNA? Indeed this is the miracle of the Almighty GOD. How could some acids combine together to run out such a great plan? [14]

The cell division is also an astonishing process as the information of about 1 million pages divides and forms another cell in just a few minutes, is indeed an amazing process.

DNA has a very special way of dividing and combing. When cells divide, the DNA ladder splits down from the middle. There are then two single vertical strands, each with the half of the rings. Both now duplicate themselves instantly, and there are now two complete ladders where a moment before

there was but one. Each new strip has exactly the same sequence that the original strip of DNA had. This process of division can occur at the amazing rate of 1000 base pairs per second. If DNA did not divide this much quickly, it could take 10,000 years to grow from that first cell to a new born infant. Human cells can divide more than 50 times before dying. When they die, they are immediately replaced. Every minute 3 billion cells die in our body and replaced immediately. [15]

DNA is found in the nucleus of cell. When the cell divides, formation of DNA is also essential during this division. The details for this are that the DNA is a huge treasury of information in which every detail regarding the living organism is present. If would like to copy this information on pages in the form of words, it would take us 3 trillion words written on 1000 series of an encyclopedia. When the cell divides, the information written on DNA is transferred to the DNA on the other cell. It takes about 20-80 minutes for this transfer. Imagine 3 trillion words transferring completely without any mistake, amazing.

While Darwin and his followers deny this stunning miracle by saying that all this is formed by itself and without any creator. But all the order, setting and beauty of this universe totally denies this thought. It can be clearly understood that without any creator the idea of creation is not at all a consent. Because Darwin presented this idea and died. But the way this idea is being supported and is being tried to keep it alive there must be some special reason behind this. Another important fact is that at the time of presenting evolution theory the science and technology were not as advance as today. Even seeing a bacteria was not possible because scientists used simple instruments for investigation in the laboratories. Therefore some of the misunderstandings and wrong perceptions developed, which severely affected the minds of common people. But with the passage of time science developed amazingly and the scientists disclosed the most important and new declarations about the cell which were even inconceivable in Darwin's time. [16]

No doubt that Almighty God is revealing his signs on us. This widespread and endless universe is also a great sign and a great book. Quran order again and again to read this book of universe with deep thinking. The existential symbol in the body of human beings and in living creatures in the form of DNA has also been revealed. Despite of all these

facts, if someone denies the existence of God, will be same as denying the sun in a blatant day.

The whole of the system is under command of DNA. Whatever command DNA will pass will be accepted by the cell. For example, the DNA will direct the cell to make up the protein and it will be formulated. The proteins are very complicated chemicals in the cell. For the preparation of proteins, the directions present in the shape of codes on DNA. The tasks or directions are also known as genes. What is protein? Proteins can be understood by a simple example, as different colors of pearls are lined up in a specific way i.e. comprising two white pearls then four red pearls then five blue and a white lastly in a single line. The composition of these pearls can be considered as that of protein. Suppose it is the protein of cow. The composition of fish will be different than that of cow. Similarly, the composition of protein in every animal is different from that of the other in formulation. The cell consists of many amino acids but 20 specific kinds of amino acids make protein. Where would each protein be used, all such details are present on the DNA of each cell. Where the DNA itself gets these directions from? Or who issues these directions? Science is unable to answer such questions. Indeed He is the Almighty Allah who is the creator of this stunning process, He is Allah who writes on these tiny invisible threads in a hidden font and in these writings have all the directions which are necessary for a simple cell to make a whole new human being. All these directions are written from four chemical components. These are actually the first alphabets of four chemicals i.e. A.T.C.G. adenine, thiamine, guanine, cytosine. Like the combination of words form a sentence and combinations of sentences form books, similarly the book of life is sequenced. By different sequences of these four chemical components (A.T.C.G) a word (means by the combination of amino acids a type of protein) is formed. By the combination of many words (different types of proteins) sentences (tissues) are formed. The combination of different types of tissues results into a whole new body. This body could be of any organism starting from an ant to a whale, from a babul tree to a rose plant or even from a quadruped to a human being. This is the will of the Almighty Creator whether he creates a human being, any animal or a rose plant in this manner. These directions called codes or genes, are the ones which decide all the details like how much will the individual live, which diseases will he suffer from, how will he die, all such details, directions, orders are present in each and every cell (except the red blood cells) in a hundred trillion cells.

Genetics is a new study. This study deals with the analysis of reasons of differences in humans such as shape and features, habits and manners, and height and stature. Why the cubs of cat aren't same as the kits of rabbit? Why the infants of animals start walking immediately after birth? Why don't the children have same features as that of the parents? The answers of all such questions could be given by the study of genetics or genetic engineering. These answers were not in the studies of earlier scientists. Why are the faces, statures, natures and colors of trillions of human beings different? All of these differences are due to a contradiction of 0.1% in the human genes while 9.99% genes in all human beings is identical. If that 0.1% contradiction didn't exist, all the human beings would be identical to each other. Due to this 0.1% change the shape and features, skin, height and stature, voice, nature, diseases, weaknesses, and even the finger prints do not match with any other human on this whole planet. Since today none of the individuals are born with same finger prints as that of the others. All these differences are only due to genes.

In the upcoming days it's being tried to save an infant from many diseases even before it's born. This can be possible by changing in the genes, which is termed as genetic engineering. In this manner, changes are being done in fruits and vegetables. By making changes in genes, new and better properties can be produced in fruits and vegetables, which were not present in them earlier, for example, the genes of a fish found in freeze seas which saved it from freezing was transfer in the DNA of strawberry. It was concluded that in the strawberry which used to rot due to cold weather, a property was developed, which prevented it from rotting. There is a kind of a vitamin which is not found in rice. When the genes of a specific flower were transferred in the DNA of rice, they became sufficient in the respective vitamins, which are known as golden rice. The nutrition obtained from such process is called genetically modified, shortly GM, which is being positively used in the lots of ways.

After making some change in the DNA in plants farther experiments were conducted in animals. By cloning in the animals a sheep named dolly was borne. It was born in 1966 and died in 2004. This process was named as nuclear transfer. However, it was a genetic program still it was not the scientist created the dolly sheep. It is also true that before the dolly sheep the nucleus transfer process was experimented on 277 genes among which only the dolly sheep was successful. In the experiment of dolly sheep scientists collected only those cells from

the female sheep which played their role in fertilization, the nucleus was extracted from the cells obtained from another sheep. Those cell without nucleus were inserted in the nucleus of egg cells of another sheep by the help of an electric shock the egg cell became a part of the other cell. Then these started to increase in number by cell division. Then this embryo was transferred in the womb of sheep. The dolly sheep took same time to borne as the other infants.

Birth of dolly does not proves this that the specialists of genetics can bring any dead body to life. Scientists even after having all the knowledge cannot bring bacteria to life. It's only the almighty God who brings bodies to life. The followers of the theory of evolution just have their ego and stubbornness with them. They do not have any scientific evidences to prove it because science also was some basic rules, which the scientist have to follow. [17]

Cell and the treasury of information's are pointing towards the stunning system of DNA. In the nucleus of each cell are 46 chromosomes. In the chromosomes of each cells about 10 billion of those DNA ladders. Scientists called each spiral ladder a DNA molecule; they also call them base pairs. It is the sequence of chemicals within these base pairs that provides the instructional code for our body. That instructional code oversees all our heredity and many of our body metabolic processes. The question arise here how this complicated structure of DNA begin? But it's a displeasing movement that the followers of evolution theory possess such a childish thinking about this. According to them:

There was some mud on earth and near it some water was also present. There was lightening in the sky. Suddenly the lightening fell on to the mud and water, from which living organisms came into being, with fully prepared DNA. Those organisms not only had a complete system of DNA but also were immediately being able to eat, digest their food, move and perform other functions properly. The cell of these organisms knew how to divide. Only by the fall of lightening their bodies were differentiated into male and female pair and their complete digestive, respiratory and circulatory organs. It provided them with complete ability to produce offspring and they in turn more offspring. That same stroke of lightning also made their food with its own entire DNA, male and female pairs, etc.

DNA is an extremely complex chemical molecule. Where did it come from? How did it form back in the beginning? If university trained scientists, working in

multi-million-dollar equipped and stocked laboratories, cannot make DNA and RNA, how can random action of sand and dirty water produce it in the beginning? [18]

Today we know that DNA of human body has information of an encyclopedia, almost consist on ten lakhs pages. Could it possible that billions of words are spread on the road and form these words best thesis appear? Is it possible by chance? Followers of evolution theory think that “Chance” is best and superior power, who has created the wisdom of human wisdom, and this power is responsible for material and mental characteristics. But it is fact that all these arguments are lie and totally wrong. Fact is, Almighty God is the creator of everything.

The theory of evolution suffered a lot due to the discoveries of 20th century. A group of Darwin’s followers, while proving their loyalty to Darwin, started to find solutions for these problems. The experts of zoologists and botanists attended the conference held under the supervision of geological society of America. There scientist overviewed the objections raising on theory of evolution. [19]

Thus after the old theory of evolution being badly failed. The followers of the theory tried to give a solution to this problem by presenting a new idea named neo Darwinism in the end 1930. For this purpose they added the sudden change (Mutation) in it. According to the Cambridge advanced learner’s dictionary, mutation is defined as: The way in which GENES change and produce permanent differences. [20]

The presenter of neo Darwinism explained that the reason behind the sudden change in genes is, the interference of external factors, like radiation etc. This means that all the living bodies presented on the earth are a result of this sudden change (Mutation). Where by all the extremely complicated organs, such as eyes, brain, lungs and heart etc. of all the animals and humans are a result of the same sudden change. In other words this change is due to the genetic disorder. [21]

It is well known among many knowledgeable scientists that if evolution could possibly occur ever, mutation would have to accomplish it. There is simply no other mechanism that can make change within the DNA. Natural selection consists failed, so sudden changes (mutations) are the last hope of the majority of evolutionists today.

Mutations generally produce one of three type of changes within genes or chromosomes. 1. An

alteration of DNA letters sequence in the genes. 2. Gross changes in chromosomes (inversion, translocation), or 3. A change in number of chromosomes (polyploidy, haploidy). But whatever the cause, the result is a change in genetic information. Here are some basic hurdles which that scientists must overcome in order to make mutation a success story of evolution: 1. mutation must occur quiet frequently, 2. Mutation must be beneficial, at least some times. 3. They must effect a dramatic enough change (involving, actually, millions of specific, purposive changes) so that one spices will be transformed into another. Small changes only will damage or destroy the organism. [22]

“Changes” would and immense impotence in the theory of evolution. According to these assumptions, because of changes occurred in the genes of organisms accidently or due to the influence of environment. One type of specie changed into another specie. [23]

Lynn Margulis is distinguished university professor of biology in the University of Massachusetts. Lynn Margulis is highly respected for her widely accepted theory that mitochondria, the energy source of plant and animal cells, were once independent bacterial cells. And Lynn Margulis says that history will ultimately judge neo Darwinism as, a minor twentieth century religious sect within the sprawling religious persuasion of Anglo-Saxon biology. At one of her many public talks she asks the molecular biologists in the audience to name a single unambiguous example of the formation of a new species by the accumulation of mutation. Her challenge goes unmet. [24]

DNA not only transfers all information present in it without any fluctuations or changes from one cell to another or from one generation to another belt always keeps this information safe. However the experts of genetics do believe that on the basis of some reasons very minute changes occur in genes (directions). Sometimes it could be possible due to different rays, chemicals or radiations, but such changes are destructive not constructive. It means that the occurred changes would be harmful instead of it would be beneficial. And it is not possible at all that these changes would change one specie to another or would form any new specie.

In reality, mutations have four special qualities that are ruinous to the hopes of evolutionists. 1. Mutations are very rare. 2. Mutations are always random, and never purposive or directed. 3. Evolution requires improvement. Mutations do not help or improve; they

only weaken and injure. 4. Nearly all mutations are harmful. In most instances mutations weaken or damage the organism in some way so that it (or its offspring if it is able to have any) will not long survive. But now the situation is worse. In order to prove these sudden changes thousands of mutation experiments have been done. In a determined effort to prove the possibility of evolution by mutation. And this is what they learned: Not once has there ever been a recorded instance of a truly beneficial mutation, nor such a mutation that was permanent passing on from one generation to other. [25]

The changes caused due to radiations were deadly and harmful, and this can be acknowledge by some incidents which were seen in the past. During the world war two the two cities of Japan, Hiroshima and Nagasaki were attacked with atomic bombs. Due to bombing, severe radiation spread in the area. By this radiation many people were found in a very bad situation or found to be dead. Moreover the people in its range remained influenced with its effect for years, the radiation of atomic bomb badly affected the people, till many generations their infants were borne handicapped, and a similar incident took place in a city of Russia, Charnobail in 1986. When because of an explosion in their nuclear plant, the radiation spread in whole area, even the impact of radiation reached to the west as well. Likewise Japan people were either found dead or get disabled. [26]

In biochemistry a mutation is change in DNA. To be inherited, the change must occur in DNA of a reproductive cell of DNA. The simplest mutation occurs when a single nucleotide (nucleotide are the building blocks of DNA) in creature's DNA is switched to a different nucleotide; alternatively a single nucleotide can be added or left out when the DNA is copied during cell division. Sometimes though, a whole region of DNA- thousands and millions of nucleotides – is accidentally deleted or duplicated. A well –known mutation called antennaphedia that scientist can produce in laboratory fruit fly: the poor mutant creature has legs growing out of its head instead of antennas. [27]

RESULTS:

The result of this discussion is that the life was originated spontaneously, has a great impact on the lives of thousand people. This is a theory which explains the origin of universe and life without a creator. By the deep scientific research of cell and DNA we came to know that it is not possible that anything could come into existence by itself.

In the previous pages we came to know that cell is an amazing even we should say a miraculous tiny entity.

There is a highly complexed, planned structure is working in it. So the claim of evolutionists that it can be formed by a coincidence, is wrong. If something could be happen by chance, we the most intelligent among all the creatures defiantly can be produce that thing. Coincidence can only result in chaos, disruption, disorder, error and freaks of nature. The magnificent harmony, order, balance and aesthetic nature of cell and other living things show that they are all the product of a knowledgeable and faultless creation. However, when we examine all of the different components of cell, as DNA, ribosomes, mitochondria, enzymes and hormones, they all are highly active and carry amazing processes very intelligently.

As we are doing something, the molecules in our bodies have been going about their activities constantly. Some have measured the calcium level, others have begun collection of amino acids necessary for protein production, some are dividing the DNA's double helix in order to copy it. How it all happening? It's not logical to say that this intelligence is actually a property of cell itself, because the components of cell are nothing more than a group of molecules, in fact they don't have brain. So what is the source of intelligence? If a drone can be controlled by thousands of miles, it does not mean that it is the intelligence of drone plain. The intelligence displayed by ell or any other component of nature did not come about by itself. It is the intelligence of God.

This whole unique system is witness for a great creator and everything proves the existence of a great planner. In the past it was tried to use science as anti-religion (Quran) but the science is the name of, study of nature and a person who is in search of truth, science will definitely show him the light of truth.

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